

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Orthodontics is the most sought-after dentistry specialization in the Philippines: A descriptive study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Google trends (GT) is one way to investigate the search trends of the interest of people in some branches of dentistry. This study aimed to compare the search trends of Filipinos for orthodontics, endodontics, oral and maxillofacial surgery (OMFS), pediatric dentistry (PD), and prosthodontics from 2012 until 2022. **Methods:** Using GT, search parameters using the keywords “orthodontics”, “endodontics”, “oral and maxillofacial surgery”, “pediatric dentistry”, and “prosthodontics”, the Philippines as country, 2012-2022 for time range, health as category, and web search as database was used. **Results:** The search trends showed that orthodontics was the most searched topic with its highest peaks (100%) in April 2019 and August 2019. Followed by OMFS with its highest peak (34%) in September 2014. PD ranked third out of the five topics with its highest peak (39%) in September 2012. Next is endodontics with its highest peak (24%) in June 2014. The least searched topic is prosthodontics having its highest peak (25%) in June 2017. **Discussion:** The search for OMFS, PD, endodontics, and prosthodontics was relatively low compared to orthodontics from 2012-2022 in the Philippines. **Conclusions:** The Filipinos were more interested in searching online for orthodontics than the other four specializations.

Keywords oral surgery, maxillofacial surgery, endodontics, pediatric dentistry, orthodontics, prosthodontics

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1 | Introduction

The oral cavity is the interface between medicine and dentistry and a patient's window to their overall health.

Numerous illnesses and drugs can affect the oral cavity, and pathologic disorders in the mouth have a more significant systemic result than many health care providers could realize.¹ For most people, any doctor who provides dental care is thought of as a Dentist. They believe that dentistry only deals with one part of the body

(mouth). They say “Oral health is overall health”. However, dental treatment is often neglected and put at the bottom of their priority list due to lack of knowledge about its importance.² Dentistry is a wide field, it takes six to eight years before you finish the degree. And, just as with your overall body health, the dentists’ work extends beyond the dental chair. They are often the first health care to recognize and identify a wide variety of diseases --- they are members of the primary health care professions on the front line of disease prevention, intervention, and wellness promotion ranging from hypertension to oral cancer up to taking precautions with pregnant women and person with special care.³

Every profession, but perhaps more so the medical field, engage in ongoing self-evaluation intending to develop their field in a predictable and quantifiable way. The goal is to improve patient health, increase efficiency in the health care system, and enhance society as a whole. And for the dentistry profession, this change is particularly true. Since the Doctor of Dental Medicine (DMD) or Doctor of Dental Surgery (DDS) was founded the profession has rapidly changed and expanded. They have undergone significant transformation in the last several years including the significance of dental post-graduate specializations. In fact, they are

characterized by geometrically (if not logarithmically) increasing combinations and arrangements of equipment and instruments.⁴ A variety of dental health practitioners provide different services and have different areas of focus.

Specialization in dentistry must be appropriate for any country to fulfill its four main objectives—to provide a solid dental educational foundation, to meet the needs of special patients, to respond to the complex needs of society on behalf of the dental profession, and to meet the development needs of individual dentists.¹

Furthermore, due to technological advancements, tremendous changes have resulted in the field of dentistry. Patients can research freely about the treatment they can avail themselves with growing awareness of the esthetic appearance of the face and teeth patients are seeking more options to choose from.⁴ Making Orthodontics at the top of the list.

In addition, Google Trends (GT), a cutting-edge tool with quick and anonymous tracking capabilities that predicts public interest, GT can help research and monitor social and medical.⁵ Google trends help dental professionals to know what the current trends in society are. Training professionals with a solid specialization based both on cultural insights and

Figure 1. Interest over time of Filipino internet searches for dental specializations (Orthodontics, Endodontology, OMFS, PD, and Prosthodontics) from 2012-2022.

hands-on clinical activities translates into the possibility of making true prevention. This would enable dental professionals to offer patients the best treatment possible while also emphasizing the value of prevention in general.

This research will help the field of dentistry in many ways possible and it will also show Filipinos' search for different branches of Dentistry from the year 2012 until the present time.

2| Results

2.1 Interest over time of Filipino internet searches for dental specializations

The Filipinos searched highest for orthodontics in April 2019 and August

2019 at 100%, while Endodontology had its highest search with only 24% last June 2014. OMFS had its highest search in September 2014 with 34%, while PD had its highest searches with 39% last September 2012. Prosthodontics, being the lowest searched topic out of the 5 specialties, had its highest search last June 2017 with only 25% (Figure 1).

2.1.1. Orthodontics

The interest of the Filipino people in Orthodontics already existed during August 2012 with an average of 52%. The highest searches were done in April 2019 and August 2019 at 100% and presently at 77% in July 2022 (Figure 1).

2.1.2. Endodontology

Figure 2. Compared breakdown by sub-region of Filipino internet searches for dental specializations (OMFS, Endodontics, Cosmetic dentistry, Orthodontics, and Prosthodontics) from 2012-2022

The interest of the Filipino people for Endodontics already existed during August 2012 with an average of 16%. The highest search was done in June 2014 at 24% and presently at 11% in July 2022 (Figure 1).

2.1.3. Oral and maxillofacial surgery
The interest (0%) of the Filipino people for OMFS was non-existent during August 2012. But increased to an average of 15% last October 2012. The highest search was done in September 2014 at 34% and presently at 15% in July 2022 (Figure 1).

2.1.4. Pediatric dentistry

The interest of the Filipino people for PD already existed during August 2012 with an average of 12%. The highest search was done in September 2012 at 39% and presently at 8% in July 2022 (Figure 1).

2.1.5. Prosthodontics

The interest (0%) of the Filipino people in Prosthodontics was non-existent in August 2012. But increased to an average of 11% last September 2012. The highest search was done in June 2017 at 25% and presently at 3% in July 2022 (Figure 1).

2.2 Compared breakdown by sub-region

In terms of the highest searches for Orthodontics, the first ranked sub-region is Northern Mindanao (100%), followed by Cagayan Valley (100%), Zamboanga Peninsula (100%), Region XII (100%), and Caraga (100%). For interests in Endodontics, the top regions are CAR (23%), Western Visayas (13%), Metro Manila (11%), Davao Region (11%), and Central Luzon (10%). Highest searches for OMFS shows that ARMM (23%) is the first ranked sub-region followed by Ilocos Region (18%), Davao Region (16%), Central Visayas (14%), Metro Manila (13%). Sub-regions that have the highest searches for PD are Calabarzon (13%), Central Visayas (12%), Metro

Manila (11%), Central Luzon (11%), Davao Region (11%). For interests in Prosthodontics, the top regions are CAR (10%), Metro Manila (7%), Central Luzon (6%), Central Visayas (6%), and Calabarzon (4%) (Figure 2).

3 | Discussion

In this study, strengthening the reporting of observational studies in epidemiology (STROBE) reporting guideline (<https://bit.ly/3AK88w5>) was used to facilitate proper discussion of the results.⁶

The majority of the Filipinos chose orthodontics as the most-sought after dentistry specialization. According to the results, the highest peak of search values for orthodontics is at 100% followed by OMFS at 34%, PD at 39%, prosthodontics at 25%, and endodontics coming in last at 24%.

Orthodontics was the specialization of the most searches in sub-regions such Northern Mindanao, Cagayan Valley, Zamboanga Peninsula, Region XII, and Caraga. The Ilocos region, the Davao region, Central Visayas, and Metro Manila appear to have seen the most OMFS searches. The majority of PD searches were in the Central Visayas, the vicinity of Davao, and Calabarzon. The CAR, Metro Manila, Central Luzon, Central Visayas, and Calabarzon regions all showed a lot of interest in

prosthodontics. Endodontics is the most searched for in the CAR, Western Visayas, Metro Manila, Davao region, and Central Luzon regions.

In the past ten years, of all of the dental specialties, orthodontics has received the most online searches. Orthodontics is the only dental specialty that appears to be well established in the Philippines. About hundred orthodontists are currently in practice from 2009 to present, and either has advanced degrees or have completed training courses that have been approved by the Philippine Board of Orthodontics.⁷ The development of self-esteem and social acceptance in contemporary society depends greatly on having healthy teeth and a pleasing smile.⁸ It follows that the patients' requests for aesthetic enhancement are reasonable. After periodontal and tooth caries, the third most prevalent disease in dentistry is malocclusion. Malocclusions are a major global public health concern due to the detrimental effects they have on patients' physical, social, and psychological health.⁹ This is the rationale behind why the majority of Filipino patients prefer orthodontics to other disciplines.

Simple tooth extraction is one of the most common operations in oral and maxillofacial surgery.¹⁰ Because of their ignorance, several Filipinos instantly suggest extractions when they experience tooth pain and discomfort. However, as people's

understanding has grown, more of them are preferring to seek other treatment alternatives before opting for extraction.¹¹ Furthermore, OMFS presents challenging cases that general practitioners are unable to handle, making it the second-most sought-after specialization in the Philippines. Even though pediatric dentistry is the third most searched dental specialty, young children's oral health is still not given enough consideration. A variety of poor oral health behaviors were predicted by parents' knowledge and attitudes. More diseased teeth may be a sign that parents are less knowledgeable about how to raise their children to have healthy teeth.¹² This indicates that dental education is necessary for both parents and their children because it is still one of the top oral health issues in the Philippines.

According to the result, prosthodontics is the next-to-last dental specialty that Filipinos search for online. It provides a range of treatments, including the creation of crowns, bridges, inlays, onlays, veneers, partial and complete dentures, and implants.¹³ However, because it is thought that the treatments offered are expensive, the majority of Filipinos to some extent disregard this specialty. Dentures are the only form of treatment for the majority of Filipinos, particularly those from lower socioeconomic classes.¹⁴

The field of endodontics, on the other hand, the most frequent reason people seek dental care is pain, which a root canal procedure may be used to address.¹⁵ The choice to treat a patient, however, was relatively subjective and subject to a variety of influences, including the community, one's employment, socioeconomic standing, values, and practices.¹⁶ Individuals have been acting under the notion that there are challenges involved with receiving a root canal, including pain. Numerous worries are raised, and these frequently result in postponing appointments at the dental clinic. Many patients admit that they experience tension due to the anticipated endodontic procedure.¹⁷

The results reported herein should be considered in light of some limitations. The comparison of different branches of dentistry is limited only to orthodontics, endodontics, OMFS, PD, and prosthodontics. The results are only based on 2012–2022 in the Philippines. They are therefore subject to the biases and preferences of Filipinos during a time period that may have influenced the results. The study made use of Google trends, which limits the search to other search engines like Microsoft Bing and Yahoo. The specializations are chosen according to the six recognized specializations in the Philippines, which are regulated by different organizations accredited by

the Professional Regulation Commission. These are orthodontics, PD, endodontics, periodontics, prosthodontics, and OMFS. The study is confined to orthodontics, endodontics, OMFS, PD, and prosthodontics due to the limitations of keywords restrained by GT. The research used GT as the tool to gather the results but restricted the searches from other search engines. GT is a useful and reliable source of information for the study.

4 | Methods

4.1. Data acquisition

The Google Trends website was accessed on August 13, 2022. The terms “prosthodontics”, “oral and maxillofacial surgery”, “endodontics”, “pediatric dentistry”, and “orthodontics” were used. The parameters that were chosen were Philippines as country, 2012-present as time range, health as category, and web search as database. The STROBE reporting guideline were utilized in this study for discussion of the results.

4.2. Statistical analysis

Descriptive analysis was done directly from the graphic user interface of Google Trends. Data were expressed in percentages.

5 | Conclusions

The Filipinos were more interested in searching online for orthodontics than other specialties of dentistry. Although the search for oral and maxillofacial

surgery (OMFS), endodontics, pediatric dentistry (PD), and prosthodontics had been recognized by Filipinos since 2012, the trend implies that from 2012 to 2022, orthodontics had been the leading search term. Other branches of dentistry have also been explored by Filipinos but didn't go beyond the interest in orthodontics.

Dental schools can use Google Trends to investigate the search trends or interests of Filipinos for branches of dentistry. This can benefit dental schools by knowing what people are more inclined towards. They can use this information to build a connection with students to pursue what they like in the future and strive to provide a higher quality education for Filipino dental students. This feature can be used by dental students as well as dental schools to learn about what people seek. This gives them an idea of what branch of dentistry they can study and learn more about.

Author Contributions

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Validation, A.M., J.C., C.D.; Formal
analysis, A.M.; Resources, A.M., R.Q.,
J.C., C.D.; Original Draft, A.M., R.Q.,
E.V., J.C., C.D.; Review & Editing, A.M.,
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Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in
accordance with the Declaration of
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Committee of Southwestern
University PHINMA School of
dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from
the patient and the attending dentist.
All methods have been exhausted to
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patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of
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